

QUIZ**LAST NAME: ADELEKE****FIRST NAME: OLUWANIFISE****PROGRAM CODE: DILT****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR GULMA**

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes)

The author used Zotero to insert references

The author used the following software: (MSWord 2019 on MacBook)

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. **What citation style does Kate Turabian's Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses and Dissertations document?**

 Chicago.¹ MLA. Harvard. Oxford.

2. **Write the parenthetical form for this entry: Lindsay Moir, *The Law of Internal Armed Conflict*, 1st edition (Cambridge, UK ; New York: Cambridge University Press, 2002), 20.**

 (Lindsay Moir 2002, 20). (Lindsay 20).

¹ Kate L. Turabian et al., *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Eighth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, Eighth edition (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 10.

- (Moir 2002, 20).²
- (Moir 2002 20).
3. **When you paraphrase, summarise, or mention an author's work, you do not have to give a reference.**
- True.
- False.**³
- Only give reference when the author's work is mentioned.
- None of the above.
4. **Which of these four citation styles uses footnotes and endnotes?**
- Turabian Style.
- Bibliography Style.**⁴
- Reference List Style.
- Oxford Style.
5. **What are the two most common ways of citing articles in the Turabian style?**
- Bibliography and endnote style.
- Author-date and footnote style.
- Parenthetical style and author-date style.

² Ibid., 87-88.

³ Ibid., 53.

⁴ Ibid., 87.

Bibliography style and author-date style.⁵

6. **What style guide does Euclid recommend for writing?**

Chicago Rules (Turabian).⁶

Harvard Rules.

Oxford Rules (OSCOLA).

APA Rules.

7. **Which of these best describes a literature review?**

A short essay of the theoretical background to a research study.

A detailed list of articles and other published materials that describe a research study.

A literature review involves the systematic identification, location, and analysis of material related to the research problem.⁷

An Internet search for articles that describes relevant research about a methodology and research problem.

8. **The starting point for any research project is all but one of the following:**

Identification of a research problem.

⁵ Ibid.

⁶ Laurent Cleenewerck and Dr Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA- 401D Coursepack: Period 1.*, 2nd ed. (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019), 24.

⁷ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie F. Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map From Beginning to End*, Second edition (Thousand Oaks, Calif: SAGE Publications, Inc, 2012), 46.

- Identification of data and reporting findings.**⁸
- Identification of research questions.
- Identification of a research topic.
9. **All but one of the following is true about the scope of a literature review?**
- A literature review should cover every material on a research topic.**⁹
- A literature review should represent the most current work undertaken in a subject area.
- A literature review should at least cover five years.
- A literature review should only cover the works that are directly related to a specific research problem.
10. **One of the following is untrue about the emphasis of qualitative research.**
- It emphasises on exploration.
- It emphasises on discovery.
- It emphasises on description.
- It emphasises on revelation.**¹⁰

⁸ Bloomberg and Volpe, 2–7.

⁹ Bloomberg and Volpe, 49.

¹⁰ Bloomberg and Volpe, 8.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

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Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Dr Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA- 401D Coursepack: Period 1*. 2nd ed. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019.

Turabian, Kate L., Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, and University of Chicago Press Staff. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Eighth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Eighth edition. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.